

DEMOGRAPHIC, ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL (NON)COHESION IN RURAL AREAS IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract: *The Macedonian village is in a phase of renovation, i.e. it is no longer homogeneous but has a distinctly complex social structure. The village comes out of its isolation and sets more and more demands for the daily development of (non-economic) institutions and services that will meet the needs of the current and future standard of living. However, the development process in the rural areas does not generate enough jobs of satisfactory quality and variety to retain young people who want to stay in the community. A growing number of young people avoid the agricultural occupation, so a significant number of households are already without youth, and therefore without an heir. The emigration also causes a number of significant phenomena of a social nature. First of all, this directed to a negative increase of population, creation of aging households, i.e. households without young, without the possibility to reproduce. These households in rural areas reduce the production to the level necessary to satisfy their personal needs, and with the aging process, they abandon a large part of their own capacities (land) and reduce the livestock. The upsurge in the number of individual agricultural holdings in the conditions of the aging of the rural population and the depopulation of the villages indicates the fact that the current state of the agrarian and rural policy is in a low-quality phase of development. How that smallholder sector will be trained for efficient and marketable agriculture is still uncertain. The purpose of this paper is to show social cohesion as a precondition for a certain socio-economic development of the village. Social cohesion is a broad concept whose creation is influenced by numerous policies that encourage social inclusion and social mobility.*

Keywords: *economic and social cohesion, rural development, inequity, rural policy*

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1. Introduction

The services provided by the public sector in the rural areas are inefficient, there is a sense of collapse of the environment, distrust in the government, depression, reduced social organization, declining services from the private sector, empty houses, poor living conditions, lack of social and cultural content for young people and closing public institutions (schools, clinics, post offices and shops). Agriculture is the only source of income, which cannot sustain the micro system and diverse needs of the population. The poor are not poor because they live in certain environments, but because they have low incomes, a lack of goods and services, and that their social power is low. On average, agricultural households spend 52% of their available funds on food and soft drinks. According to Orshansky, people are poor if more than 30 percent of the household budget is spent on food (Orshansky, 1969).

Besides the low incomes, the huge dissatisfaction of the population in those areas arises from the underdeveloped communal infrastructure (roads, water pipes, etc.). This is especially characteristic of distant settlements from the city, which do not have paved roads, do not have public transport, cannot use services in education, health, etc. Who are forced to invest more funds for the use of communal and social infrastructure services. For these people who live in these environments, also there is a limitation of the opportunities to participate in the economic life. They earn less income than those who live and work in cities, have more difficult access to the financial institutions, to use the services of the state administration in opening a business and similar. The lack of a clear development policy towards the village leads to the backwardness of many rural regions (especially those that have retained an agrarian character, and are located outside the gravitational zones of urban environments). It leads to strong depopulation and in some places to real social and demographic depression. Due to spontaneous migration, many rural municipalities have been completely evicted (205 or 12%, census 2021), which sets a serious and far-reaching task for the revitalization of at least one part of those regions before the State. It can be expected that some regions, especially villages with up to 10 inhabitants, will be completely displaced, and there are 218 such villages. A significant part of the rural population leaves their native homes not only for economic reasons, but also because of the greater infrastructural opportunities of urban areas, due to the need to educate their children, the need for health care, due to the fact that they hope to get jobs in the future, etc.

There are 177.845 individual agricultural holdings and 280 business entities operating in the Macedonian agriculture, and one production subject has only 1.5 ha of used agricultural land (as of 2016 year).

Table 1. Agricultural holdings by utilized agricultural area

							Total number	Average size
	< 1ha	1-3ha	3-5ha	5-8ha	8-10ha	>10ha		
2013 year	58.30	29.44	7.31	2.90	0.82	1.23	170581	1.6
2016 year	60.94	26.67	7.65	2.48	0.74	1.32	177845	1.5
2013=100	105	91	105	85	90	107	104	94

Source: My calculations, State Statistical Office, Statistical Review: Agriculture, No. 5.4.15.01/803, 2015 and No. 5.4.17.02/888, 2017, Skopje.

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Namely, on average at the state level, the size of land holdings continues to decrease, so that in 2016, compared to 2013, the category up to 1 ha increased by 4%, and the average size of individual agricultural holdings decreased by 6%. The development so far and the world experience have shown that: small private agricultural holdings are economical only to a certain extent at the expense of high labor intensity. It is shown that farmers with small holdings cannot be competitive and apply scientific and technical achievements in agriculture. A rising number of young people avoid the agricultural occupation, a significant number of households are already without youth, and therefore without an heir. The data show that the vital power of family farms is declining, namely the participation of persons under 34 years of age has decreased from 25% in 2013 to 22% in 2016.

There are no results from the Law on Land Consolidation (Official Gazette 187/2013), the number of parcels per individual agricultural holding remains with an average of around 7 parcels or the average size of one parcel is 0.14 ha. These tendencies are anti-economic in origin, caused by the huge weaknesses in the land policy in Macedonia.

The rural policy in the Republic of North Macedonia is a classic example of government failure. The reason is that the economic policy has been built around key industries and not communities for the last three decades. In these years, the main comparative advantage is placed on resources, such as cheap location, cheap labor, more relaxed regulations. The small villages, having a small number of inhabitants, cannot offer greater or significant local diversity, so the economic base of these villages, if not entire districts, becomes very vulnerable to the slumps. Furthermore, these conditions are related to the greater distance between rural households, as well as between economic activities, which increases the costs of transportation. That is why rural areas that are close to urban areas fare much better than rural areas that are far away. The underdeveloped road and communication infrastructure increases the costs subsequent from the geographical distance.

2. Understanding the cohesion

The term cohesion refers to the degree of connection and integration within the community i.e. it represents mutual trust and reciprocity relying on the common norms. Referring to the indicators of altruism, trust and the degree of assistance, some authors see the economic, technological and cultural changes within the framework of post-industrial development as the causes of the crisis in social cohesion, which is especially noticeable in poverty and disintegration in the local communities in which they live population with a lower economic and educational status. (Cars and others 1998).

The Council of Europe defines the cohesion as: "Ability of society to ensure the well-being of all its members, by modifying inequality and preventing polarization" (Council of Europe, 2004, p.3)

The OECD considers a cohesive society: "If it is about the well-being of all its members, if it is about fighting against their social exclusion, if it creates and nurtures a sense of belonging in society, it encourages trust and offers its members the opportunity for upward social mobility." (OECD, 2011, p.28)

That means, if society wants to achieve the cohesion through social inclusion, then it should focus on solving poverty, inequality and social polarization. Also, society can choose to achieve cohesion through the creation of social capital, that is, institutions, relationships and values that influence the interaction between people and thereby contribute to economic and social development (World Bank, 1998, p.1). Creation of such an environment that will encourage different forms of civic organization and building high interpersonal and social trust. Some communities can achieve social cohesion through the promotion of social mobility.

The European Union has also set the social cohesion as a purpose. The social cohesion was declared as one of the three key strategic objectives of the European Union at the Lisbon Summit of the European Council in 2000. The European Union encourages its members to become cohesive communities, i.e. to achieve balanced and harmonious development, primarily reducing social and economic differences between regions.

3. Aspects the affect the cohesion

3.1. Education is one of the key policies for the cohesion

The education result affects all dimensions of the cohesion: social inclusion, social capital and social mobility. Reducing the number of uneducated or low-educated people is a significant means of fighting inequality and fighting for achieving higher incomes (OECD, 2011).

Education affects not only through the process of socialization that takes place in the school, but the results of the educated and indirectly affects equality in the distribution of income, which in return creates social cohesion in society. In addition to access to education, the quality of education is also important for social cohesion. Fundamental features in increasing incomes and the well-being of the population are the quality of education and the progress in knowledge. "The future of the population is not determined by space, energy and arable land. It will be determined by the intelligent development of human possibilities" (Schultz, 1982, p.15). A higher level of education implies greater knowledge, a higher quality in the performance of work tasks, a broader view of the world, greater security in keeping a job, a better quality of life, greater social involvement, while a low level of education points toward to a low standard of living and a lower quality life and social exclusion.

In the past period, certain results have been achieved, but still the educational structure of persons engaged in individual agricultural holdings is far from the average of those persons in non-agricultural households.

Table 2. Educational structure of persons employed on individual agricultural holdings

Degree of education	2013 year	2016 year
Total	100.00	100.00
Incomplete primary and secondary education primary and lower secondary education	47.17	45.17
Secondary education (agricultural)	3.23	3.87
Secondary education (other)	41.27	42.77
Higher and university education (agricultural)	0.92	0.95
Higher and university education (other)	7.41	7.24

Source: State Statistical Office, Typology and structure of agricultural holdings, 2013, Statistical Review: Agriculture, 5.4.15.01/803 p.118 and Structure and typology of agricultural holdings, 2016, Statistical Review: Agriculture, 5.4.17.02 / 888, p.73, Skopje.

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The data in 2016 show that 45.2% of people are without education, with incomplete primary education and with primary education. The participation of persons with secondary agricultural education is remarkably low (3.9%) comparing to the participation of persons with other secondary education (42.8%). The apprenticeship of people with higher and higher agricultural education is about 1%, which is much lower compared to the apprenticeship of people with other higher and higher education (7.2%). The relatively low share of the population with higher education is, among other things, the result of the migration of highly educated staff. Namely, individuals who are more educated are more mobile. They are looking for a job that matches their skills, abilities, education and expectations and that will pay back the investment in education. But it should also be noted that access to services, especially education, affects migration, which in turn has a negative impact on the reduction of the population in rural areas, especially the young population, which has led to the closing of many schools due to lack of children. Children from villages that are close to urban areas, larger villages, villages that are well connected to the city and that have good infrastructure and access to education have the opportunity to go to school and return to the village. While children from mountain villages and underdeveloped areas do not have such an opportunity, due to lack of basic infrastructure, underdeveloped road communication, they have no other choice but to migrate permanently together with the whole family or during the school year to sit at home or look for other activities. Also, one of the basic obstacles for the education of children from rural areas is the insufficient and low income of the families, which is more pronounced in the mountain villages, namely this situation has a long tradition in Macedonia. This means that when we talk about the education of the population, we mean the population that lives in villages that do not have road and traffic infrastructure and have low incomes, while their social capital and mobility are low compared to the general population, so through education in the long term the best social cohesion can be promoted.

3.2. Unemployment has a devastating impact on the rural development

Easterlin believes that full employment can increase happiness in society (Easterlin, 2013). The OECD study shows that the quality and type of work affects the average level of life satisfaction differently, that is, full-time employees are "significantly more satisfied than other forms of employment" (OECD, 2011). Access to work and employment affect "the sense of belonging in society and the perception of fairness" (World Bank, 2012, p.126). In other words, "the unemployed participate less in society and have little confidence" (World Bank, 2012, p.131). Society should do the best to create full employment which is a "key component of well-being". (Barr, 2012, p.7).

Earning from paid work is the largest source of income, while lack of earnings is the largest cause of poverty (Sutherland et.al, 2003). Changes in employment status or earnings are a major cause of movement into or out of poverty (Jenkins and Riggs, 2001).

However, the correlation between poverty and the tendencies in the structure of the labor force is significant, it can even be said to be co-existent. "In conditions where there are no, or there are only a small number of sources of material support, it is clear that exclusion from paid work leads to poverty" (Alcock, 2006, p.80).

The position of the rural population in some regions of the Republic of North Macedonia is significantly different from the position of the urban population. Namely, the unemployment rate in the Polog Region (21.2%) does not give good prospects for the social integration of the population, especially if we bear in mind the unemployment rate in the rural part, which is 24.2% (Regions in the Republic of North Macedonia 2024). This means that nearly a quarter of the workforce in the rural part of the Polog Region is prevented from getting a wage and work experience. The high unemployment rate indicates the absence of social cohesion.

3.3. The inequality is one of the main reasons for low cohesion

A certain level of minimum wealth and development, such as the necessary fulfilment of the basic needs of individuals with the required level of resources is required for existence of a cohesive society. When society reaches a certain level of economic minimum, other factors take over the role of developing cohesion in society, such as the level of trust, legitimacy of institutions, participation of citizens in social movements, level of equality or sense of belonging in society (Jenson, 1998; Bernard, 1999).

Populations in rich countries are happier on average compared to poor ones, and a correlation can be established between an increase in income and an increase in life satisfaction. However Inglehard (1997) believes that income brings happiness up to a certain level of development, further economic growth has little effect on the average subjective feeling of well-being.

Inequality in rich and poor countries mostly comes from the income (OECD, 2012). High inequality poses a great danger to social cohesion. According to Wilkinson, Pickett, (2010, p.45), the inequality "weakens community life, reduces trust and increases violence".

The disparity in access to services (education, water supply, sewage roads) weakens the quality of life in the community and reduces trust. Access to local services can affect and be affected by people's living standards. Although the quality of local services has the capacity to improve the living standard of the population, the importance of departmental services differs depending on the level of income. Insufficient availability or inequality and financial impossibility often represent an obstacle to the use of public and private services. Poor households typically face lower quality services, or poverty further embeds limitations in service use.

Empirical research indicates that the level of provision of services and products in rural areas is very low. No significant results have been achieved of the vital problems and needs of the people in the village since the influence of the local Government in the immediate initiation and resolution is very low. On average, the rural population is mostly dissatisfied with the work of the local government in creating new jobs (52.40%) and opportunities in culture and sports activities (51,20%) (Jakjimovski, 2017, p.1057).

The percentage share of the funds for improving the quality in rural areas in the total funds for rural development are another confirmation of an inadequate policy for dealing with social exclusion. From the planned funds (11 430 894 euros) for the measures of financial support for rural development for 2025, most of the funds are intended for the measure 121 "investments for the modernization of agricultural holdings" (50.4%) and for the measure 124 "investments in the infrastructure for development of agriculture, forestry,

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water management and protection of natural resources" (5.0%). While only about 163 000 euros or 1.4% are planned funds for measure 321 "improving the quality of life in the countryside" (construction of local road infrastructure, construction of water supply and sewage systems, construction of facilities and equipment for homes for children and youth, construction and modernization of livestock markets), for measure 322 "village reconstruction and development" about 2.4% or 276 423 euros and for measure 323 "preservation and promotion of traditional values in rural areas" 1.4% or about 163 000 euros which indicates rural development without improvement of living conditions which is consistent with increasing rural poverty and isolation (Program for Financial Support of Rural Development in 2025). The methodology of the revitalization of these areas is not sufficiently known, and without sufficient quality analyzes and information, there are no ideas to realize it. The approach is usually designed from an ineffective, schematized and extremely unprofessional and bureaucratic procedure. Rural development policy measures must correspond to the strategy for progress and show positive results.

4. Conclusion

The rural areas are too reliant on the employment in the agrarian sector and this is precisely the reason why we have low incomes, poverty and spatial migration. In rural areas where most of the labor force is located in the food production sectors, the number of those who have an university education is low, and most of the young people who finish the secondary education, immediately intend to start a work with a wage in this sector.

The future of the rural areas will be determined by these two factors: attracting activities that offer higher wages and improving of the services. Orientation to employment outside the farm and awareness of the importance of the non-agrarian sector are key conditions for the movement of the rural populace along the paths of upward social mobility. Employment in the non-agricultural sector brings significant advantages: constant monthly income, pension and health insurance and favorable social status. Investments in road infrastructure and the extent of modern telecommunications links to rural areas can play a significant role in improving the long-standing problems of the remoteness and location. These systems will help rural areas overcome isolation and bring villages closer to mainstream ecosystems. Rural areas that depend exclusively on the natural resources have always had a problem with economic progress and social cohesion. If close links with urban areas are achieved, the social cohesion in the rural communities will be improved, rural population with low education and unemployment will be reduced and attention will be paid to the amenities offered by the natural resource sector - such as tourism and recreation. Any other form of rural development represents a set of circumstances that would be short-lived and as any rural failure without social cohesion is expected. It is necessary to shift strategies from a traditional economic basis (natural resources and production) to sectors that provide a new economic basis - tourism and recreation. These are the basic criteria that lead us to the notion of integral development as a comprehensive approach to the progress of the rural environment. The developed countries have realized the need for a comprehensive approach and invest a significant effort in the integral development of rural areas before a long time ago. It is necessary to identify poor areas at the local level and provide special funds for them, in order to eradicate social isolation. It is essential, to review all systemic solutions and measures of economic and social policy and to establish specific solutions and differentiated

measures in accordance with the specific conditions in individual rural areas, types of settlements and types of households, based on the determinations of the Constitution.

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DEMOGRAFSKA, EKONOMSKA I SOCIJALNA (NE)KOHEZIJA U RURALNIM PODRUČJIMA U REPUBLICI SEVERNOJ MAKEDONIJI

Rezime: *Makedonsko selo je u fazi obnove, tj. više nije homogeno, već ima izrazito složenu društvenu strukturu. Selo izlazi iz svoje izolacije i postavlja sve više zahteva za svakodnevni razvoj (neekonomskih) institucija i usluga koje će zadovoljiti potrebe sadašnjeg i budućeg životnog standarda. Međutim, proces razvoja u ruralnim područjima ne generiše dovoljno radnih mesta zadovoljavajućeg kvaliteta i raznovrsnosti da bi se zadržali mladi ljudi koji žele da ostanu u zajednici. Sve veći broj mladih ljudi izbegava poljoprivredno zanimanje, pa je značajan broj domaćinstava bez mladih, a samim tim i bez naslednika. Emigracija takođe uzrokuje niz značajnih pojava društvene prirode. Pre svega, ovo je usmereno na negativan priraštaj stanovništva, stvaranje starijih domaćinstava, tj. domaćinstava bez mladih, bez mogućnosti reprodukcije. Ova domaćinstva u ruralnim područjima smanjuju proizvodnju na nivo neophodan za zadovoljavanje ličnih potreba, a sa procesom starenja napuštaju veliki deo sopstvenih kapaciteta (zemljišta) i smanjuju stočni fond. Porast broja individualnih poljoprivrednih gazdinstava u uslovima starenja seoskog stanovništva i depopulacije sela, ukazuje na činjenicu da se trenutno stanje agrarne i ruralne politike nalazi u nekvalitetnoj fazi razvoja. Kako će se taj sektor malih poljoprivrednika osposobiti za efikasnu i tržišno isplativu poljoprivredu, još uvek je neizvesno. Cilj ovog rada je da pokaže socijalnu koheziju kao preduslov za određeni socio-ekonomski razvoj sela. Socijalna kohezija je širok koncept na čije stvaranje utiču brojne politike koje podstiču socijalnu inkluziju i socijalnu mobilnost.*

Ključne reči: *Ekonomska i socijalna kohezija, ruralni razvoj, nejednakost, ruralna politika.*